

Assessing bike-transit accessibility with OpenStreetMap

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Low-density land use, sprawl, and Euclidean zoning (i.e., separation of commercial and residential land-uses) can reduce the effectiveness of public transit by reducing the number of homes, amenities, services, and jobs near transit stops [1,2]. This gives rise to the first-last mile problem, where transit riders must travel long distances to access transit from their origin and from transit to their destination. Bicycles as a first and/or last-mile mode (henceforth referred to as bike-transit) can extend the service coverage area of a transit stop or station by allowing transit users to cover a greater distance in the same amount of time [3]. Not only can people reach transit stops faster on a bicycle than they could by walking; people using bicycles can also reach more transit stops within the same time frame. Lastly, people may be able to avoid bus feeder routes and cycle directly to higher service quality transit routes (such as rail).

Despite bike-transit's potential for shortening travel times, bike-transit is not commonly modeled in traditional travel demand modeling or trip planners. This is because bike-transit trips are computationally intensive to calculate given the number of possible transit stop pairs and departure times. Our solution to this is to use bicycle and transit shortest path algorithms to demonstrate how bike-transit improves public transit's accessibility to destinations by reducing overall travel times, transit waiting times, and the number of transit transfers needed. Previous work has been done in assessing how bike-transit improves the effectiveness of public transit [4-7]; in this case, we will take an in-depth look at three different locations that are varying in distance from bus and heavy rail service in Atlanta, Georgia, USA.

To develop our network for bike routing, the street network for the study area was retrieved from OpenStreetMap (OSM) through Osmnx and Overpass API. The OSM data were filtered to only include public roads and multi-use paths that allowed bicycle travel. Static GTFS data from the Metropolitan Atlanta Rapid Transportation Authority (MARTA) was used for transit shortest path calculation. Supplementary data from the Atlanta Regional Commission's 2022 Regional Bicycle Facility Inventory were used to add cycling

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infrastructure not present in OSM. The final network was composed of 366,926 links and 323,275 nodes. Traffic analysis zones (TAZ) from the Atlanta Regional Commission's (ARC) 2020 activity-based model run served as potential origins and destinations. There were a total of 2,221 TAZs in the study area. In the case presented here, three TAZs were selected to represent the variability in transit service and land use throughout the study area. Three visualizations on accessibility, travel times, and transit mode(s) utilized are generated for each location to communicate the increase in accessibility from bike-transit for that area. The utilization of the transit network has not been examined in previous studies measuring bike-transit accessibility. Two configurations of bicycle first-last mile travel are considered: bringing the bicycle aboard transit to have the bicycle for biking at both ends of the trip (bike-transit) and leaving the bike at the first stop (bike-transit-walk). The optimal routes to all possible destinations in the transit service area are calculated for walk-transit, bike-transit-walk, and bike-transit.

The walking and biking portions of trips are modeled using Dijkstra's algorithm [8], and the transit portion is modeled using the round-based public transit optimized routing (RAPTOR) algorithm [9]. The walking and biking routing steps only considered travel time as an impedance, leaving out a number of potential attributes that pedestrians and cyclists consider in choosing a route such as elevation, the number of turns, and the presence of sidewalks/cycling infrastructure [10]. MARTA heavy rail stations at the extents of the study area tend to be park-and-ride oriented, and residential/commercial development around these locations is limited. The streets surrounding these stations are large, high speed roads that are not comfortable to cycle on or walk next to. As such, the current model likely overestimates the number of accessible areas. In future studies, these attributes need to be incorporated to more accurately assess bike-transit accessibility.

However, most of the road attributes that would enhance bicycle routing are not currently available in OSM. For this study, there were 467 unique OSM attributes (keys) present in the network data, yet most of the values for these keys were empty. When just examining public roads (excluding restricted access roads, service roads, and bicycle/pedestrian paths), there were 293 unique attributes. Figure 1 shows that most of these attributes were also empty. Attribute completion was calculated by adding the lengths of all roads with non-empty values for a particular attribute and dividing by the total length of all the roads. Meta attributes such as *highway* and *osmid* were completely filled out, but essential attributes for calculating bike impedances such as the number of lanes, the speed limit, and the presence of street parking had low completion values of 16%, 13%, and 0.1%, respectively. Other key attributes for cycling routing such as percent grade or incline were not present in the data at all.

Since these attributes are not available through OSM for many areas, researchers currently have to seek data from municipal or private sources. In the former case, the availability and quality of municipal data varies widely by jurisdiction. Municipal data on streets with the desired attributes were not available for this abstract's study area. In the latter case, private data are often cost-prohibitive and cannot be shared widely, which limits the repeatability of research results. Another approach is to impute necessary data based on OSM's *highway* key. The People for Bike's Bicycle Network Analysis tool uses this approach to impute the number of lanes and the speed limit [11]. However, this could lead to inaccurate routing if the imputed data is incorrect. Other attributes, such as street parking, are more difficult to impute using just the *highway* key.

Figure 1. Attribute completion weighted by road length and rounded to the nearest percent (N = 293).

In the future, there should be a more concerted effort by OSM contributors, researchers, and organizations to fill in these attributes. This would allow researchers to develop more nuanced routing algorithms for cycling, walking, and transit use. However, for this abstract, bike-transit accessibility was assessed without these attributes. Current results indicate that bike-transit and bike-transit-walk decrease travel and wait times for transit, and in many cases reduce the number of transfers required compared to walk-transit. Transit services with higher travel speeds or frequencies such as heavy rail, greatly increased the geographic extent of accessible destinations and reduced travel times. Thus, an origin's distance to rail service had a major impact on the number of accessible TAZs.

Again, these results likely overestimate the extent of bike-transit accessible areas due to the lack of attributes relevant for using cycling-specific routing impedances. Future research, in addition to incorporating cycling specific impedances, will need to balance these impedances against public transit-specific impedances (which is also currently set as a time-only impedance). For example, even with two transit routes that provide an equivalent total transit link travel time, the route with the shorter wait time will likely be scored by users as having lower impedance (most users penalize wait time more than travel time in their mode choice decision-making) [4]. Additionally, if the bike route to access the transit route with the shorter waiting time had a higher impedance than the other transit route, some users may endure the higher impedance bike route to access the route with shorter wait time. Cyclists may also have public transit-specific preferences that can also be accounted for in estimating impedance, such as a preference for rail service over bus service and/or avoiding transfers. More research is needed to bring in specific mode impedances for transit and walking into overall impedance calculations.

Despite the limitations of this research, these results suggest that planners and engineers should consider bike-transit-walk and bike-transit in their planning and travel demand modeling processes to maximize the utilization of their existing transit network. Planners and engineers can repeat the analyses presented in this research to identify where bike-transit would be most effective. Additionally, this methodology can be used to assess

how public transit service changes and new cycling infrastructure can impact the accessibility of bike-transit trips. Other first-last mile modes such as bike-share and scooter-share can also be assessed.

However, efforts should be made by researchers, contributors, and other organizations to complete OSM's attribute data. This would allow planners and engineers to more accurately assess where the potential for bike-transit trips is greatest, so that measures that increase accessibility of these trips (secure bicycle storage and bicycle infrastructure) can be introduced. In many cases, adding cycling infrastructure to existing roadways will be less costly and more timely than transit-oriented development or new transit service. In addition, encouraging bike-transit trips could replace automobile trips and reduce transportation greenhouse gas emissions and vehicle miles traveled. Lastly, because bike-transit is a complicated mode due to the large number of potential transit stop and route combinations, transit operators should also work to provide mobile trip planners that offer step-by-step bike-transit routing. Widely used trip-planning apps do not include this option for most areas, which makes it difficult for travelers to plan these trips.

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